

Farm machinery

Effect of water depth on field capacity and field efficiency of soil preparation equipment

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We used minitractor, animal, and human power to prepare fields for transplanting in a study of differences in field capacity and field efficiency.

Treatments were no standing water and 5-10 cm and 15-20 cm water depth, in a factorial design with 3 replications.

Experimental plots were 25 × 20 m at Lanrang Experimental Farm in 1983 dry season. Highest average field capacities were as follows: minitractor, 0.156 ha/h; animal power, 0.111 ha/h; and human power, 0.092 ha/h, with respective field efficiencies of 72.7, 79.9, and 63.9% (Table 1, 2). □

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Farming systems

Performance of rice varieties intercropped with pigeonpea

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We studied the performance of three rice varieties intercropped with pigeonpea (Type 21) in a randomized block design with 3 replications in 1987 wet season. Soil was sandy loam, with

Table 1. Effective field capacity of soil preparation equipment at 3 water depths (0, 5-10 cm, 15-20 cm). Lanrang, Sidrap, Indonesia, 1983.

Power source	Land preparation ^a	Effective field capacity ^b (ha/h)		
		0	5-10 cm	15-20 cm
Minitractor	Phase 1	0.067 a	0.136 c	0.084 b
	Phase 2	0.077 a	0.130 b	0.133 b
	Phase 3	0.132 a	0.201 b	0.155 ab
	Mean	0.092 a	0.156 c	0.124 b
Bullock (1 pair)	Phase 1	0.026 a	0.035 a	0.031 a
	Phase 2	0.030 a	0.037 b	0.032 a
	Phase 3	0.150 a	0.260 c	0.210 b
	Mean	0.069 a	0.111 c	0.091 b
Manual labor (5 men)	Phase 1	0.027 a	0.039 b	0.049 b
	Phase 2	0.123 a	0.114 a	0.093 a
	Phase 3	0.116 a	0.123 a	0.093 a
	Mean	0.089 b	0.092 b	0.078 a

^aPhase 1 = rotary plow and mini tractor, plow and bullocks, hoe and manual labor; phase 2 = rotary plow, plow, hoe; phase 3 = rotary plow, harrow, hoe. ^bIn a row, numbers followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at 5% DMRT.

Table 2. Field efficiency of power for land preparation at 3 water depths (0, 5-10 cm, 15-20 cm). Lanrang, Sidrap, Indonesia, 1983.

Power source	Land preparation ^a	Field efficiency (%)		
		0 cm	5-10 cm	15-20 cm
Minitractor	Phase 1	31.3	63.6	39.3
	Phase 2	36.0	60.7	62.1
	Phase 3	61.7	93.9	72.4
	Mean	43.0	72.7	57.9
Bullock (1 pair)	Phase 1	61.9	83.3	73.8
	Phase 2	71.4	88.1	76.2
	Phase 3	39.5	68.4	55.3
	Mean	57.6	79.9	68.4
Manual labor (5 men)	Phase 1	18.8	27.1	34.0
	Phase 2	85.4	79.2	64.6
	Phase 3	80.6	85.4	64.6
	Mean	61.6	63.9	54.4

^aSee footnote^a in Table 1.

Rice and pigeonpea yields in monocrop and intercrop. Uttar Pradesh, India, 1987.

Treatment	Rice yield (t/ha)	Pigeonpea yield (t/ha)	Land equivalent ratio
Single crop Arhar T21		1.86	1.0
Single crop rice NDR84	1.8	—	1.0
Single crop rice NDR118	1.5	—	1.0
Single crop rice Narendra 1	2.0	—	1.0
Rice NDR84 + Arhar T21	1.4	1.27	1.49
Rice NDR118 + Arhar T21	1.3	1.28	1.58
Rice Narendra + Arhar T21	1.7	0.98	1.43
LSD (P=0.05)	0.6	0.40	
CV (%)	13.1	6.69	

pH 7.5 and 0.58% organic matter.

The 170-175 d pigeonpea cultivar and short-duration rice cultivars NDR84,

NDR 118, and Narendra 118 were sown as single crops and intercrops. Spacing (60 cm between rows and 20 cm between

plants) and seed rate (20 kg/ha) for pigeonpea single crop and intercrops were the same.

Single crop rice was direct seeded at 100 kg seed/ha in 15-cm rows. Intercropped rice, seeded at 75 kg seed/ha, had 60-cm row spacing.

Fertilizer was applied at 60 kg N, 13 kg P, and 25 kg K/ha.

All P and K and 25% N were applied basally. The remaining N was applied to rice 50% at 20 d and 25% at 40 d after seeding.

Grain yields were 1.8 t/ha for single

crop rice and 1.4 t/ha for intercropped rice (see table). Mean pigeonpea yield was 1.9 t/ha for single crop and 1.2 t/ha for the intercrop. The mean land equivalent ratio was 1.5, indicating considerable increase in resource use efficiency. □

A rice - grain legume cropping system for South Coastal Orissa, India

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We studied yields of five rice - grain legume cropping systems with varying fertilizer levels. The dry season crops were green gram *Vigna radiata*, black gram *Vigna mungo*, cowpea *Vigna*

unguiculata, peanut *Arachis hypogaea*, and wheat *Triticum aestivum*. No crop (fallow) was maintained for one treatment to study the nutrient uptake of wet season rice.

Soil was sandy loam with pH 5.63, 0.25% organic C, 95 kg available P (Bray)/ha, and 375 kg exchangeable K/ha. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with four replications, with crops in the main plots and N levels in the subplots. Rice variety Pratap was transplanted on 10 Aug 1986 at 20- × 10-cm spacing with 40-60 kg

PK/ha applied as basal. N was applied in 2 splits at 0, 30, 60, and 90 kg/ha. Harvest was on 19 Nov 1986.

Dry season crops were sown 26 Dec 1986. Grain legumes and peanut received 20-40-0 and wheat 120-60-40 kg NPK/ha. Half the N and all the P and K was basal, the remaining N was topdressed 20 d after sowing. Preflowering and postflowering irrigations facilitated growth.

Rice - peanut and rice - black gram had the highest total grain yields, closely followed by rice - wheat (Table 1).

Total rice grain yield increased with N, but there was no significant difference between 60 kg N/ha and 90 kg N/ha.

Soil organic C percentage increased with the cropping patterns (Table 2). Available P and exchangeable K decreased in rice - black gram (which had the highest total grain production). □

Table 1. Grain yield of wet season rice and succeeding dry season crops. Orissa, India, 1986-87.

Cropping system	Wet season rice grain yield (t/ha)	Dry season crop grain yield (t/ha)	Total grain produced (t/ha)	Total variable cost (\$/ha)	Total return (\$/ha)	Total profit (\$/ha)	Cost-benefit ratio
Rice - cowpea (C-152)	3.9	0.68	4.50	676	953	277	1.41
Rice - green gram (Berhampur local)	4.0	0.26	4.23	583	768	185	1.32
Rice - wheat (Sonalika)	4.0	0.61	4.59	722	900	178	1.25
Rice - black gram (T-9)	4.4	0.68	5.07	600	1048	448	1.74
Rice	4.3	—	4.29	478	686	208	1.43
Rice - peanut (Ak 12-24)	4.1	1.07	5.13	820	1244	423	1.52
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	0.32	—	—	—	—
<i>N levels</i>							
No N	3.6	0.52	4.10	—	—	—	—
30 kg N/ha	4.1	0.54	4.63	—	—	—	—
60 kg N/ha	4.2	0.57	4.81	—	—	—	—
90 kg N/ha	4.4	0.56	4.98	—	—	—	—
LSD (0.05)	0.1	ns	0.14	—	—	—	—

Table 2. Soil test value after dry season crop. Orissa, India, 1986-87.

Cropping system	pH	Organic C (%)	Available P (kg/ha)	Exchangeable K (kg/ha)
Rice - cowpea	5.57	0.43	125	255
Rice - green gram	5.35	0.31	161	342
Rice - wheat	5.40	0.28	125	242
Rice - black gram	5.65	0.30	137	155
Rice - fallow (no crop)	5.70	0.33	147	227
Rice - peanut	5.60	0.35	125	227
Initial soil test value	5.63	0.25	95	375

Rice-based cropping sequences for northwestern Himalayas uplands

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We compared 7 irrigated upland rice-based intensive cropping sequences with traditional rice - wheat/potato sequences on VPKAS experimental fields (1,250 m). The experiment was conducted 1982-85 in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Three cycles were completed.

Soil was loamy with neutral pH and medium fertility. Recommended